

**Francesca Coppa,
Professor of
English, Theatre
and Film Studies,
Muhlenberg College**

Open access helps new voices be heard

– Francesca Coppa

Open access helps academics think differently – about how research outputs like books are created and shared, and how different voices are surfaced and represented

Open access publishing encourages diversity and inclusivity. This is very important to Francesca Coppa, Professor of English, Theatre and Film Studies at Muhlenberg College in the US.

Openness and transparency

One of the founders of the Organization for Transformative Works (OTW), an initiative that started as the largest all female open source coding project on the Internet, Coppa has always experimented with new, open ways of working. OTW is all about open culture and open access and it has been very successful – one of its projects, The Archive of Our Own, is a popular global entertainment website, according to Coppa.

She said:

“Through publishing open access, the Internet is not only a place of commerce, but a place of making and sharing good information and art.”

Remix cultures

Coppa is a strong advocate and lobbyist for remix cultures, for fair use practices and for less restrictive copyright. Her most recent book *Vidding: A History* focuses on fan-made videos. She was determined it would be available not just to academics but also to the community of artists the book is centred around and to any other interested parties, especially students, who she believes need to see a more diverse array of artists. The book explores a grassroots feminist art form of people making videos and sharing them freely, so it was inconceivable to Coppa that it would go behind a paywall.

Enabling new forms of creative expression

If Coppa's book had been published within the standard confines of academic publishing, Coppa says it wouldn't have worked.

Her scholarship focuses on transmedia storytelling, exploring the interplay between text, theatre, video and image. It was vital that her research output reflected that - the online version is multimedia, including 150 videos, clips, images and links. Those videos, clips, images and links are integral to the research and Coppa's exploration of vidding. They also make for much more dynamic, useful materials in a teaching context.

This was only possible because the digital format enabled the content to be embedded within the book. But hosting so many videos was expensive. Fortunately for Coppa, her college was very supportive and helped her apply for grants to cover those costs.

Coppa also has good connections in the transmedia storytelling community so getting permissions to host content was quite straightforward. But she says a culture of fair use in the US and fair dealing in the UK is important to enable an open access culture to flourish.

Finding the right publisher

When choosing a publisher, Coppa says academics need to look around to establish the options available. She recommends talking to university librarians as they are

often extremely knowledgeable about which presses have strong support for open access. They may also have suggestions about how to obtain grants or funding.

If an academic wants to experiment with form and content, as Coppa has done, she says they need to be prepared to lead the conversation and find out what is possible. She said:

“ There are many resources for open access book publishing if a scholar thinks to ask the question. This can also be a conversation you have with an acquiring editor.

Bringing research into the classroom

There is a whole section in Coppa’s book dedicated to teachers. It is important to Coppa that teachers can use material that is of interest to them and share it flexibly with students as a link or transfer it to a smartboard in the classroom.

She thinks open access and open source hugely benefit underrepresented communities, enabling fresh voices and fresh perspectives to be heard.

She said:

“I don’t want to have any more barriers to people bringing diverse work into the classroom than there already are. It’s an inclusivity issue – that’s how you get the voices of people who are not mainstream artists into the classroom.”

Making scholarship visible and accessible

Coppa thinks the academic community needs to be realistic about how people access knowledge and information today. If research is out of reach, behind a paywall or in an expensive book, then many people will read and reference what they find freely through search engines. This has the effect of reducing the impact of individual research and individual authors and reducing the dissemination of scholarly findings.

But if research is freely available, then people find it and read it, as Coppa has found.

She said:

“People are citing it and using it and teaching it, which is what I wanted.”